

Emotional competence: A conceptual review

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Abstract:

Emotional competence, a term used synonymously with emotional Intelligence, describes a person's ability to express emotions with complete freedom. Competence is the level of skill with which a person interacts constructively with other people. The concept is based on emotional intelligence, and a person who wants to be emotionally competent is expected to possess a reasonable level of emotional Intelligence. The growing significance of the concept can be understood because most professional organizations these days are using psychometric tests to assess the prospective employee's attitudes. A positive person and emotionally competent person can be an asset to the organization. On the other hand, emotionally incompetent persons can be a burden. This paper carries a short review of the concept along with some of its key dimensions.

Keywords: Emotional competence, emotional intelligence, Daniel Goleman

Introduction

Emotional competence refers to the necessary social skills to recognize, interpret, and respond positively and constructively to our own emotions and those of others. Huy (1999) and Saarni (1999) have stressed that a person's ability to experience, manage, and direct emotions within social situations should have a sense of purpose and appropriateness. "Emotional competence" (Saarni, 1999) and "emotional capability" (Huy, 1999) are concepts that precisely captured the notion that individuals and groups manage their emotions purposively, in the sense that they express people's individuality and the capacity to cope with emotionally challenging situations, while at the same time behaving following organizational goals and norms. However, little work has been done to operationalize the concepts of emotional competence or capability.

Difference between emotional competence and emotional Intelligence

Emotional competencies are related to and are based on emotional Intelligence. A certain degree of emotional intelligence is necessary to understand emotional competence. For instance, identifying another person's accurate feeling enables one to master a specific competency like influence. Similarly, people who are good at regulating their emotions find it easier to develop a competency like initiative (Cherniss 2000).

While emotional intelligence may not be a strong predictor of job performance, it does provide the foundation for emotional competencies that are a strong predictor of job performance. Goleman (Emmerling and Goleman 2003) represented this idea by distinguishing between emotional competence and emotional Intelligence. Emotional competence means the personal and social skills that enable superior performance in the professional world.

Despite the difference between the two, the term emotional competence is quite regularly equated with the term emotional Intelligence. Emotional Intelligence was closely associated with job efficiency in the context of a study of bank managers. The same was justified because “there is a relationship between the nature of the bank manager’s job and personnel’s knowledge level, attitude, motivations, and have an understanding of client views” (Mohmmad Shahhosseini et al., 2012).

Emotional Intelligence

The ongoing years have seen the quick modification towards globalization and competitiveness among a handful of business organizations. Along these lines, these associations can utilize another age of skilled employees to handle the movements and seriousness and battle with this circumstance. Human Resource Development (HRD) has an essential job in the officials' possibilities to be created and improved as its end is to focus on and build up the assets towards the equivalent triumph of people and associations brought by the people to the associations. As per Swanson and Holton III, 2001, two center point strings of HRD include (1) the learning of people and associations and (2) the exhibition of people and associations. The vertical part ought to be situated inside the human asset improvement perspective, and this additionally can also affect the activity execution, particularly emotional intelligence.

Professional management goes for the improvement of the human capital, particularly in their managers. They scan for approaches to enlarge the presentation separately and hierarchically. To arrive at this point, they utilize an assortment of courses. What is more, there exist opposing results in enthusiastic insight and employee performance. In this manner, dealing with this subject has the need, and like this, this examination will fill this gap and build up a hypothesis of employee performance. Research shows no connection between employee performance and emotional Intelligence theoretically in the insurance industry, as shown in the literature.

While the concept of emotional Intelligence is making rapid strides in management circles, the insurance industry is growing at a brisk pace. Organizations like the insurance company are service-based organizations, and their success depends significantly on the contribution from their human capital. In this regard, the concept of emotional intelligence and its impact on employee performance assumes importance and hence this study.

In light of the (a) research studies consulted, (b) time in history the consultation has taken place, and (c) popular culture of that time on emotional Intelligence, the subject of emotional intelligence has been defined controversially. To certain authors, emotional Intelligence is characterized as the study which searches for subjective human capacities past customary scholastic knowledge (Zeidner et al., 2004). Researchers have ordered their definition dependent on either a capacity model or a blended model. In light of the Mandell and Phewanti (2003's) capacity model, "emotional intelligence is characterized as many capacities that include seeing and thinking uniquely with data that rises out of sentiments" (p. 389). Investigations of John D. Mayer and Peter Salovey (1997) have upheld this model expressing that emotional Intelligence is characterized as "the capacity to see precisely, assess, and express feeling; the capacity to get to and additionally produce sentiments when they encourage thought; the capacity to get feeling and passionate information; and the capacity to control feelings to advance passionate and scholarly development" (p. 35).

Mayer, Salovey, and Caruso (2004) also gave the meaning of emotional intelligence as "the limit to reason about feelings to improve thinking. It incorporates the capacity to precisely seeing feelings, to get to furthermore, create feelings in order to help thought, to get feelings and enthusiastic information, and to brilliantly control feelings in order to advance passionate and scholarly development" (p. 197). On the other hand, Bar-On what is more, Goleman (1995) were the blended model pioneers, and they acquainted this

methodology concurring with their led examines. Goleman (1995) gave another definition to emotional intelligence "as the capacity to perceive and control feelings both inside oneself and inside others" (p.39), and furthermore as "A variety of non-cognitive capacities, capabilities, and aptitudes that impact one's capacity to prevail with regards to adapting to natural requests and weights" (Bar-On, 2004a, p.140). The blended model is identified with the capacity to manage the social practices, highlights, and attributes.

Development of emotional competence

Quite a few studies have brought out findings to show that emotional competence can be developed not just at a younger stage but in adults as well by subjecting the population to standard intervention programs (Kotsou, Ilios et al, 2011; Ohl, Madeline et al, 2013; Denham Susanne, et al, 2016). Practically, however it is found that it takes a lifelong journey to develop one's emotional competence. Further the enhancement in emotional competence is not a matter of one training program of a couple of coaching sessions. According to them, the concerned individual should have a strong determination in staying firm by denying all wavering to keep up himself to monitor his emotion and regulate its changes according to the accepted norms of the society. This depends on one's commitment to honest and deep self-assessment. If such consistency is achieved, the individual may develop a new kind of wisdom. He will be able to recognize the changes in his behavior along with the change in the outlook of others who are associated with him. Life will be more rewarding with easing of the expected relationships.

Additional evidences of use of training and improvement in E.I. & ESC can be found in the works of other writers as well (Boyatzis and Saatchioglou, 2008; Clarke, 2010; Kotsou et al., 2011; Martins, Ramalho and Morin, 2010; Nelis et al., 2011; Nelis et al., 2009; Reuben, Sapienza and Zingales, 2009; Sala, 2005) and Schutte et al. 2013).

Components of emotional competence

The original model of Goleman's E.I. (1995; 1998) consisted of 27 competencies. Based on research comprising of 596 individuals intended to consolidate the work of Goleman (1995; 1998) and Boyatzis (1982), the original set of 27 competencies were later trimmed down to 18 competencies. The following definition of E.I. was offered:

“Emotional intelligence is observed when a person demonstrates the competencies that constitute self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and social skills at appropriate times and ways in sufficient frequency to be effective in the situation” (Boyatzis, Goleman and Rhee, 2000).

In the discussion of this model, Boyatzis (2008; 2009) defined a competency as a capability or ability that is a set of related but different behaviors organized around an underlying construct called the intent (Boyatzis, 2008; 2009). This concept is used to differentiate different types of behaviors; for instance, that of asking questions and listening to the responses. This behavior might be with the intention of understanding another individual in order to demonstrate empathy or with an intention of just appearing interested as a means of ingratiation. The model recognizes the competencies associated with awareness of the self and others and the management of one's self and others. It is summarized in the following diagram, which is adapted from Goleman et al. (2013).

Janaki Severy (2018) has presented an extended version of Goleman's Emotional Competencies model as under:

DANIEL GOLEMAN'S EMOTIONAL COMPETENCIES

	Self (Personal Competence)	Other (Social Competence)
Recognition	<p><u>Self-Awareness</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emotional self-awareness Accurate self-assessment Self-confidence 	<p><u>Social Awareness</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Empathy Service orientation Organizational awareness
Regulation	<p><u>Self-Management</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emotional self-control Trustworthiness Conscientiousness Adaptability Achievement drive Initiative 	<p><u>Relation Management</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing others Influence Communication Conflict management Visionary leadership Catalyzing change Building bonds Teamwork and collaboration

(Source: [Janaki Severy](#), 2018)

Emotional competence and performance

Results from a study of 196 supervisor-employee pairs supported that emotional competence was positively related with proactive behaviors, and proactive behaviors were positively related with both task effectiveness and social integration. Further it was found that, proactive behaviors sizably mediated the relationships between emotional competence and work performance, even though this was largely true of followers who had a higher degree of freedom in their work ([Tae Yeol Kim et. al](#), 2009).

A study varied by C. Jayan (2006) found that of the 27 variables related to emotional competencies, the 7 variables (Adaptability, Organizational Awareness, Goal Directed Without Proper Planning, Developing Others, Trustworthiness, Job Satisfaction and Influence) in the combination could predict up to 34% of variation in job performance of managers.

Self-control and emotional resilience were considered to delay the onset of a decline in performance from excessive job demands. Social skills, reliability, conscientiousness, and integrity helped promote trust, which in turn may lead to the building of cohesiveness among the members of workgroups (R Abraham, 2010). The author further found that self-confidence, emotional honesty, and emotional resilience could promote superior

performance if positive feedback were delivered in an informative manner, and it could mitigate the adverse effects of negative feedback.

Conclusion

Emotional competence, a term used at times synonymously with emotional Intelligence, describes a person's ability to express emotions with complete freedom. It is a concept quite closely linked to emotional Intelligence. Two major dimensions of emotional competence are personal competence and social competence. Authors like Daniel Goleman have done significant work in the area of emotional competence. Continuously, organizations should assess their employees' emotional competence and train and develop them to increase emotional competence. A higher emotional competence has a positive impact on both the employee and the organization.

References:

- 1 Boyatzis, R.E. & Saatscioglu, A. 2008, 'A 20-Year View of Trying to Develop Emotional, Social and Cognitive Intelligence Competencies in Graduate Management Education', *Journal of Management Development*, vol. 27 no. 1, pp. 92-108, <https://doi.org/10.1108/02621710810840785>
- 2 Boyatzis, R.E. 1982, *The Competent Manager: A Model for Effective Performance*: John Wiley & Sons
- 3 Boyatzis, R.E. 2008, 'Competencies in the 21st Century', *Journal of Management Development*, vol. 27 no. 1, pp. 5-12,
- 4 Boyatzis, R.E. 2009, 'Competencies as a Behavioral Approach to Emotional Intelligence,' *Journal of Management Development*, vol. 28 no. 9, pp. 749-770, <https://doi.org/10.1108/02621710910987647>
- 5 Boyatzis, R.E., Goleman, D. & Rhee, K. 2000, 'Clustering Competence in Emotional Intelligence: Insights from the Emotional Competence Inventory (ECI),' *Handbook of Emotional Intelligence*, pp. 343-362
- 6 C. Jayan (2006), Emotional Competence, Personality and Job Attitudes as Predictors of Job Performance, *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, February 2006, Vol. 32, No.2, 135-144.
- 7 Cherniss, C. 2000. Emotional Intelligence: What it is and why it matters. [Online.] Available
- 8 Clarke, N. 2010, 'The Impact of A Training Programme Designed to Target the Emotional Intelligence Abilities of Project Managers', *International Journal of Project Management*, Vol. 28 no. 5, pp. 461-468, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2009.08.004>
- 9 Denham Susanne, et al., (2016). Key Considerations in Assessing Young Children's Emotional Competence, *Cambridge Journal of Education*, Vol. 46, No. 3, p299-317, 2016.
- 10 Emmerling, R.J. and Goleman, D. 2003. Emotional intelligence : issues and common misunderstandings. [Online.] Available WWW: www.eiconsortium.org/research/ei_issues_and_common_misunderstandings.htm

- 11 Goleman, D. 1995, Emotional Intelligence: New York: Bantam Books
- 12 Goleman, D. 1998, Working with Emotional Intelligence: Random House LLC
- 13 Goleman, D., Boyatzis, R. & McKee, A. 2013, Primal Leadership: Unleashing the Power of Emotional Intelligence: Harvard Business Press
<https://doi.org/10.1108/02621710810840730>
- 14 Huy, Q. N. 1999. Emotional capability, emotional intelligence, and radical change. *Academy of Management Review*, 24, 325-345.
- 15 Janaki Severy (2018), Emotional Intelligence: What it is and How it Affects Business, accessed from <http://www.invistaperforms.org/emotional-intelligence-affects-business/>
- 16 Kotsou, I., Nelis, D., Grégoire, J. & Mikolajczak, M. 2011, 'Emotional Plasticity: Conditions and Effects of Improving Emotional Competence in Adulthood', *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 96 no. 4, p. 827, <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0023047>
- 17 Kotsou, Ilios, et al., (2011). Emotional Plasticity: Conditions and Effects of Improving Emotional Competence in Adulthood, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 96, No. 4, p827-839, Jul 2011
- 18 Mayer, J. D., & Salovey, P. (1997). What is emotional Intelligence: Implications for educators. In P. Salovey & D. Sluyter (Eds.), *Emotional development, emotional literacy, and emotional Intelligence* (3-31). New York: Basic Books.
- 19 Mayer, J. D., Salovey, P., & Caruso, D. R. (2004). Emotional Intelligence: Theory, findings, and implications. *Psychological Inquiry*, 15(3), 197-215.
- 20 Mohammad Shahhosseini, Abu Daud Silong, Ismi Arif Ismail and Jegak nak Uli (2012), "The Role of Emotional Intelligence on Job Performance", *International Journal of Business and Social Science* Vol. 3 No. 21; November 2012
- 21 Nelis, D., Kotsou, I., Quoidbach, J., Hansenne, M., Weytens, F., Dupuis, P. & Mikolajczak, M. 2011, 'Increasing Emotional Competence Improves Psychological and Physical Well-Being, Social Relationships, and Employability', *Emotion*, Vol. 11 no. 2, p. 354, <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0021554>
- 22 Nelis, D., Quoidbach, J., Mikolajczak, M. & Hansenne, M. 2009, 'Increasing Emotional Intelligence:(How) is it Possible?' *Personality and Individual Differences*, vol. 47 no. 1, pp. 36-41, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2009.01.046>
- 23 Ohl, Madeline et al, (2013). Strengthening Socio-Emotional Competencies in a School Setting: Data from the Pyramid Project, *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, Vol. 83, No. 3, p452-466, Sep 2013.
- 24 Rebecca Abraham (2004) Emotional Competence as Antecedent to Performance: A Contingency Framework, *Genetic, Social, and General Psychology Monographs*, 130:2, 117-145, DOI: 10.3200/MONO.130.2.117-145
- 25 Reuben, E., Sapienza, P. & Zingales, L. 2009, 'Can we Teach Emotional Intelligence,' *Columbia Business School Research Paper*.
- 26 Saarni, C. 1999. *The Development of Emotional Competence*. Guilford, New York.

- 27 Sala, F. 2005, Do Programs Designed to Increase Emotional Intelligence at Work-Work
- 28 Schutte, N.S., Malouff, J.M. & Thorsteinsson, E.B. 2013, Increasing Emotional Intelligence Through Training: Current Status and Future Directions
- 29 Swanson, R.A. and Holton, E.F. III (2001), Foundations of Human Resource Development, Berrett-Koehler, San Francisco, CA.
- 30 Tae Yeol Kim, Daniel M. Cable, Sang Pyo Kim and Jie Wang (2009), Emotional competence and work performance: The mediating effect of proactivity and the moderating effect of job autonomy, Journal of Organizational Behavior, Volume30, Issue7, October 2009, Pages 983-1000
- 31 Zeidner, M., Matthews, G., & Roberts, R. D. (2004). Emotional Intelligence in the Workplace: A critical review. Applied Psychology: An International Review, 53(3), 371-399.